

Fig. 2. Core chip configuration for a 2-port/4-beam phased array application.

The reconfigurable chip contains 8-phased-array channels with a wideband input switching network and a reconfigurable output combining network. These input and output networks allow the chip to be configured for 4 different applications: 1) 8-antenna inputs with a single-beam output beamformer; 2) 4-antenna inputs with 2-simultaneous beamforming outputs; 3) 2-antenna inputs with 4-simultaneous beamforming outputs (example shown in Fig. 2). Additionally, the beamforming outputs can be mixed to an IF frequency before exiting the chip. Also, 4) additional mixers are placed on-chip so as to reconfigure the chip as a 2-antenna input digital beamforming receiver.

II. TWO-INPUT FOUR-BEAM OUTPUT CONFIGURATION

For this paper and due to the limited available space, we will present results on the 2-antenna input/4-beam output mode (Fig. 2), but all the other modes have similar response since they use the same core-channels. In this design, the signals are differential throughout the chip except at the RF input/output ports which are single-ended (SE). The conversion between the input SE ports and the differential circuitry is done using wideband active baluns (input) and Diff-to-SE converters (output). The input/output 2-16 GHz switches are designed to be either all passive using the 0.18 μ m CMOS technology available in this process, or using active cascode-based stages.

The 2-16 GHz channels consist of vector-modulator phase shifters (PS) based on a wideband quadrature all-pass filter network [1], and followed by a variable gain amplifier (VGA). Fig. 3 and 4 present the relevant circuits for the input active switch and vector modulator, respectively.

The channel outputs are then fed to an active 4-pole/4-throw switch to select the number of channels which are fed to the beamformer as shown in Fig. 1 and 2.

The left and right channels are first added together in a wideband active cascode summer, and these outputs pass by a switch network so as to be either added again for form 1 or 2 simultaneous beams, or routed to the output ports as 4 simultaneous beams (see Fig. 2). Note that the final summers in the 1 or 2 beam configuration are based on passive networks to maintain high linearity and avoid any power saturation in the output summer.

Fig. 3. Wideband active switch circuit used in the input network for selecting the number of channels attached to the antenna ports.

Fig. 4. 5+3 bit active vector modulator with wideband IQ generator and phase control networks.

Fig. 5. 8-element phased array chip with reconfigurable number of beams (5 mm x 2.5 mm)

III. MEASUREMENTS

The chip was fabricated using the Jazz H4 SiGe BiCMOS process with 6-layer metal stack-up. The entire chip consumes 850 mA from a 2.5 V supply for all-modes, and the effective single channel power consumption is 265 mW. The chip size is 5x2.5 mm² (Fig. 5). The measured gain and input/output return losses (RL) are presented in Fig. 6. For the 2-antenna/4-beam configuration, the gain is defined as the measured S_{21} between the output port and a single input port, with the other port left open.

The measured gain for the 2-in 4-out mode is ~10-11.5 dB at 2-16 GHz with excellent gain flatness (presented for the 0° phase setting). The chip results in a wideband input and output impedance match as shown in Fig. 6. The normalized channel phase responses are shown in Fig. 7 and no phase crossings are observed at 2-16 GHz for a 5-bit setting (an 8-bit control is

Fig. 6. Measured channel gain and input/output RL.

Fig. 7. Measured normalized 5-bit phase response.

Fig. 8. Measured NF and input P_{1dB} of the 2-antenna/4-beam configuration.

also possible). The measured RMS gain and phase error (not shown) are < 0.4 dB and $< 6^\circ$ at 2-16 GHz, with a range of $3-4^\circ$ at 6-12 GHz, ensuring a 5-bit phase response over the entire band (and a 6-bit response at 6-12 GHz). A 3-bit VGA with 8 dB linear-in-dB control with DAC circuitry is also present on each channel, and the results are not included for brevity. The chip noise figure and input referred P_{1dB} (IP_{1dB}) are also measured over frequency (Fig. 8), and the NF is 11.5-12 dB at 2-14 GHz. The IP_{1dB} is $\sim -15 \pm 1$ dBm and also shows a flat response. The NF and IP_{1dB} values agree well with simulations to within ± 1 dB. Note that other core-chip configurations result in similar gain, input and output match, NF and P_{1dB} values since this is mostly limited by the input switching network and the output active combiners.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a wideband 2–16 GHz Phased Array Receiver chip with reconfigurable beam outputs. The chip performance is demonstrated over 2-in 4-out configuration to show its unique capabilities over a wide range of frequencies. Application areas are phased-array systems requiring a variety of beams, and using the same core-chip for reduced cost and system flexibility.

REFERENCES

- [1] K.-J. Koh, G.M. Rebeiz, "An X- and Ku-Band 8-Element Phased-Array Receiver in 0.18um SiGe BiCMOS Technology" *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol.43, no.6, pp.1360-1371, June 2008.
- [2] X. Guan, H. Hashemi, and A. Hajimiri, "A fully integrated 24-GHz eight-element phased-array receiver in silicon" *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 39, no. 12, pp. 2311–2320, Dec. 2004.
- [3] D-W. Kang, K-J. Koh, G.M. Rebeiz, "A Ku -Band Two-Antenna Four-Simultaneous Beams SiGe BiCMOS Phased Array Receiver" *IEEE Trans. Microwave Theory & Tech.*, vol.58, no.4, pp.771-780, April 2010.
- [4] M. van der Vossen, et al., "Design of a highly integrated Ku-band planar broadband phased array receiver with dual polarization" in *European Radar Conference (EuRAD)*, 2014 11th, vol., no., pp.392-395, 8-10 Oct. 2014
- [5] T. Yu and G. M. Rebeiz, "A 4-channel 24–27 GHz CMOS differential phased-array receiver" in *IEEE Radio Freq. Integr. Circuits Symp.*, Jun. 2009, pp. 455–458.